

Programme for the 3rd European Carbon Farming Summit

Padova Congress, 17–19 March 2026

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ECFS26

17–19 March 2026
Padova Congress Centre
Padua
Italy

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Foreword

Europe's ambition to decarbonise its land sector will only succeed if carbon farming delivers measurable impact, genuine value for farmers, and public trust. Credibility is the foundation of scale: without trusted rules, clear incentives, and consistent data, carbon farming cannot become a mainstream part of Europe's climate strategy.

After two successful editions in Valencia in 2024 and Dublin in 2025, Padua hosts the 3rd European Carbon Farming Summit ([ECFS26](#)) from March 17th to 19th, 2026. Organised by SAE Innova and Climate KIC as part of the Project CREDIBLE consortium, and co-hosted by EIT Food (as LILAS4SOILS coordinator) and Confagricoltura Veneto, with the support of Veneto Agricoltura, the [ECFS26](#) will continue to drive the transition towards credible, regenerative and climate-smart agriculture.

The discussions in Dublin made it clear that Europe is entering a new phase of the carbon farming journey, with attention now turning to implementation and related issues such as governance, investment, and long-term market credibility. The Summit will be a moment to take stock of progress under the new Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming (CRCF) Regulation, to learn from real-world examples, and to define how markets and policies can reinforce one another. Concretely, the [ECFS26](#) will explore the following five key themes:

- *From practice to impact*
- *Thinking beyond carbon*
- *Standards, policy, and ownership rights*
- *Financing carbon farming at scale*
- *Building robust and flexible MRV.*

Through its five plenary sessions, 44 parallel sessions and workshops, as well as oral presentations, poster contributions, and many networking and discussion opportunities, the [ECFS26](#) brings together the communities driving this transformation – those designing policy, innovating technologies, exploring partnerships, financing climate action, and implementing solutions on the ground. Ultimately, the Summit is about fostering dialogues, supporting the multiple actors involved in carbon farming in coming up with concrete recommendations to overcome the current challenges and paving the way for a sustainable transformation in European food systems.

Welcome to Padua, thank you for your contributions, and enjoy the Summit!

Venue Information

The venue: Padova Congress Centre

All summit sessions will take place at the Padova Congress Centre, a modern and accessible venue in the heart of Padua's exhibition district. With state-of-the-art facilities and convenient links to nearby hotels and transport, it's the perfect setting to welcome Europe's carbon farming community.

Padova Congress Centre exterior (© Padova Congress Centre)

Giotto Room (© Padova Congress Centre)

Designed by the renowned Japanese architect Kengo Kuma, the Padova Congress Centre can host overall more than 3,000 people. 9 rooms will be available for the ECFS26, from the large Giotto room with capacity for almost 700 attendants to smaller rooms in theatre and open plan configurations.

How to reach the Padova Congress Centre

Padova Congress is located around 500 meters from the train station and five minutes by car from the highway exit. It is also easy to reach from the main road junctions and walking distance from the city centre.

Venue floor plan

Venue facilities

Room name	Type of Room	Capacity (approx.)
Giotto	Theatre, cinema	687
Mantegna 1	Theatre, cinema	237
Mantegna 2	Theatre, cinema	237
Galileo	Theatre, chairs	60
Petrarca	Theatre, chairs	96
Carraresi	Theatre, chairs	80
Palladio	Workshop 5 tables	50
Donatello	Workshop 5 tables	50
Antenore	Workshop 5 tables	50

Explore Padua

At the crossroads of northeast Italy, Padua is in a strategic location, under 30 minutes by train from Venice and well-connected to other nearby Veneto cities, from Treviso to Vicenza and even Verona. A historic university city, Padua offers a mix of culture, science, and gastronomy. Below are some highlights to explore during your stay.

[Basilica of Saint Anthony of Padua \(Il Santo\)](#)

One of Europe's most important pilgrimage churches, home to Saint Anthony's tomb and artworks by Donatello and Giotto.

[Scrovegni Chapel](#)

Giotto's 14th-century fresco masterpiece (advance booking recommended).

[Prato della Valle](#)

One of Europe's largest squares, surrounded by canals and statues.

[Basilica of Santa Giustina](#)

Grand church on the eastern side of Prato della Valle, housing the relics of Saint Justina and Saint Luke the Evangelist.

[Palazzo della Ragione](#)

Former medieval courthouse with a vast, ship-shaped wooden ceiling.

[University of Padua](#)

Founded in 1222 and once home to Galileo Galilei; don't miss the Anatomical Theatre.

[Caffè Pedrocchi](#)

The famous "café without doors", a 19th-century hub of culture and politics.

[Botanical Garden of Padua \(Orto Botanico\)](#)

The world's oldest academic botanical garden (1545), a UNESCO World Heritage Site.

[Piazza dei Signori, Piazza delle Erbe & Piazza della Frutta](#)

Three lively historic squares surrounded by markets, cafés, and medieval architecture.

[Medieval Walls and City Gates](#)

Visit the remains of Padua's ancient fortifications, including the Renaissance gate, Porta Portello.

General Themes of the Summit

The ECFS26 will revolve around five main themes and dedicated innovation sessions:

A. From practice to impact

Practical examples and results from implemented carbon farming projects

B. Thinking beyond carbon

Exploring holistic approaches that put the focus on the co-benefits (environmental and social) of carbon farming.

C. Standards, policy, and ownership rights

Untangling ownership rights, from farmers to buyers of certificates, from insetting schemes to national inventories.

D. Financing carbon farming at scale

Unlocking funding and business models to scale carbon farming.

E. Building robust and flexible MRV

Developing monitoring tools that are rigorous yet practical.

F. Innovation Sessions

Summit Programme at a Glance – Tuesday 17th

8.00 – 9.00		Registration	
		Inaugural welcome to ECFS26, with interventions from:	
9.00 – 9.30		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Saskia Keesstra (Climate KIC, ECFS26 Event Coordinator) • Tristano Bacchetti De Gregoris (SAE Innova, Credible Project Coordinator) • Hon. Francesco Lollobrigida (Italian Minister of Agriculture) and local authorities 	Giotto
9.30 – 9.45		Inspirational Opening Keynote Presentation by Kirsten Dunlop (Climate KIC)	Giotto
9.45 – 11.00		Plenary Session 1: Carbon Farming for Climate Mitigation, Biodiversity and Sustainable Agriculture and Forestry	Giotto
11.00 – 11.30		Coffee break	
11.30 – 13.00		Parallel Sessions 1	
		A1. Giving Voice to Farmers: From Practice to Proof in Carbon Farming	Mantegna 1
		A2. Improved Forest Management and Community-Led Carbon Forestry: From CRCF Integration to Investment Feasibility and MRV Innovation	Carraresi
		A3. From Ambition to Action: Adaptive Governance Systems Supporting Smart and Inclusive Carbon Farming	Palladio
		B1. Beyond Carbon: Integrating Environmental, Social, and Economic Co-Benefits into Land Use, Business, and Markets	Donatello
		C1. Integrating the CRCF into International MRV Systems and the Global Climate Action Agenda	Galileo
		D1. From Verified Claims to Scaled Action: Building the European Infrastructure for Scope 3 Carbon Farming	Giotto
		D2. From Farm to Value Chain: Scaling Regenerative Agriculture through Collaboration, Finance, and Certification	Mantegna 2
		E1. Data and Approaches for Consistent Quantification of Emissions and Removals in Baseline and Carbon Farming Activities	Petrarca
		E2. From Pilots to Practice: Building a Fair, Farmer-Empowered Carbon Registry for Europe	Antenore
13.00 – 14.30		Lunch	
14.30 – 14.45		Keynote Presentation by Alessandra Zampieri (Joint Research Center): Carbon Farming: A Pathway to Sustainable Competitiveness	Giotto
14.45 – 15.00		Keynote Presentation by Francesco Musardo (Radica, formerly Alberami): The Journey of a Project Developer	Giotto
15.00 – 16.00		Plenary Session 2: Financing the Transition: Current Trends and Emerging Opportunities	Giotto
16.00 – 16.15		Transition break	
16.15 – 17.45		Parallel Sessions 2	
		A4. Climate-Smart and Resilient Agrifood Systems Through Industry Frameworks and Robust Data Infrastructure	Mantegna 2
		A5. Enabling Carbon Farming at Farm Level	Galileo
		A6. From Soil Practice to Climate Impact: Turning Knowledge into Scalable Action	Palladio
		B2. Beyond the Farm Gate: Scaling up Carbon Interventions and Regenerative Agriculture to the Landscape Level	Donatello
		C2. Demystifying Carbon Forestry: Forests vs. Agriculture? Spot the Difference and Lessons for an EU-Ready Land Use Policy	Antenore
		D3. Scaling Credible Carbon Farming: Harmonized Measurement, Public Financing, Offset Buyers, and Co-Claiming Across the Value Chain	Giotto
		D4. Bridging Finance Streams for the Agricultural Transition: Co-Claiming of Carbon Benefits and Complementarity Between Carbon and Biodiversity Approaches in Agricultural Value Chains	Carraresi
		E3. Making It Count: Monitoring And Certification Approaches For Forest Carbon Projects and Forestry Landscapes	Mantegna 1
		E4. Data and Approaches for Consistent Quantification of Emissions and Removals in Baseline and Carbon Farming Activities (ctd)	Petrarca
17.45 – 19.15		Networking, Exhibition and Poster Session 1	

Summit Programme at a Glance – Wednesday 18th

8.00 – 9.00		Registration	Giotto
		<p>Keynote Presentations on Policy Updates by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mirco Barbero (DG ENV): Soil Monitoring Directive Implementation and Carbon Farming 	
9.00 – 9.45		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marianna Paolino (DG AGRI): The Mission ‘A Soil Deal for Europe’ • Valeria Forlin (DG CLIMA): State of Play and Next Steps for Carbon Farming Certification in the EU 	
9.45 – 11.00		Plenary Session 3: Common Objectives: Carbon Farming for Everyone?	Giotto
11.00 – 11.30		Coffee break	
11.30 – 13.00		Parallel Sessions 3	
		<p>A7. Carbon Farming in Practice: Lessons from BASF’s EU Projects and their applicability to CRCF</p> <p>A8. Unlocking Synergies Among Agroforestry Actors Through Participatory Approaches</p> <p>B3. How Smart Carbon Farming Can Build the Path for Agriculture in Wetlands</p> <p>B5. Co-Benefits for Whom? Exploring Underlying Assumptions in the Design of an Intergenerational Open Geospatial Carbon Registry</p> <p>B7. From Carbon to Carbon+Nature: Leveraging Existing Tools to Shape the Next Generation of Nature Credits</p> <p>C3. Practical Implementation of Soil Carbon Projects</p> <p>E5. Cost-Effectiveness: Harnessing State-of-the-Art Technology to Scale Viable Carbon Farming MRV</p> <p>E6. Data Sharing in Action: From Uncertainty to Trust in Carbon Farming MRV</p> <p>F1. Innovation Session 1: Measurement, Verification, Certification, and Market Mechanisms</p>	<p>Giotto</p> <p>Palladio</p> <p>Donatello</p> <p>Mantegna 2</p> <p>Galileo</p> <p>Petrarca</p> <p>Mantegna 1</p> <p>Antenore</p> <p>Carraresi</p>
13.00 – 14.30		Lunch	
14.30 – 14.50		Keynote Presentation by Panos Panagos (EUSO): Providing High-Quality Data and Developing Risk Assessment for Carbon Removals	Giotto
14.50 – 16.00		Plenary Session 4: Managing Risk in Carbon Farming: Uncertainties, MRV, Liabilities, and Insurance	Giotto
16.00 – 16.15		Transition break	
16.15 – 17.45		Parallel Sessions 4	
		<p>B4. Carbon Farming as a Public Good: Integrating Farmers, Consumers, and Policy</p> <p>B6. Carbon Farming Methodologies in Livestock</p> <p>D5. Building Public Trust in European Carbon Farming: Regulatory Support of Standards, Measurement, and Digital Infrastructure</p> <p>D6. Innovative Financial Models to Scale Carbon Forestry</p> <p>D7. Unlocking European Small Farms’ Access to Carbon Markets</p> <p>E7. Soil Carbon Modelling for Scalable and Reliable MRV: Insights from MRV4SOC and MARVIC Projects</p> <p>E8. SCF-TRUSTAI 2026: Artificial Intelligence for Trustworthy Soil Carbon Monitoring and Informed Investment Decisions</p> <p>E9. Innovations in Earth Observation (EO) for Carbon Farming MRV systems</p> <p>F2. Innovation Session 2: On-the-Ground Impact, Regenerative Practices, Biodiversity, and Ecosystem Co-Benefits</p>	<p>Palladio</p> <p>Petrarca</p> <p>Mantegna 2</p> <p>Giotto</p> <p>Donatello</p> <p>Galileo</p> <p>Antenore</p> <p>Mantegna 1</p> <p>Carraresi</p>
17.45 – 19.15		Networking, Exhibition and Poster Session 2	

Summit Programme at a Glance – Thursday 19th

8.00 – 9.00 **Registration**

9.00 – 10.30 **Parallel Sessions 5**

A9. Opportunities for Cooperation on Agroforestry Carbon Farming Between European Research Projects, and Extension to Projects Operating in Africa

B8. Bridging the Gap: Farmer-Led Innovations as True Game-Changers

B9. Beyond Carbon Farming: Measuring, Verifying and Financing Nature Co-Benefits through Robust MRV frameworks - for Farm to Wetlands and Landscapes

C4. Approaches to Designing Regional Carbon Certification Schemes

D8. Scaling Carbon Farming with Stakeholders: Trust, Certification Frameworks, and Local Initiatives

D9. Financing Carbon Farming: Insights from a Global, Regional and Local perspective

E10. Standards, Practices and Certification Approaches for Carbon Forestry

E11. Data Standardisation and Harmonisation towards Credible MRV systems

10.30 – 11.00 **Coffee break**

11.00 – 12.30 **Plenary Session 5: The Next Steps for Carbon Farming – Broadening Beyond Agriculture**

12.30 – 13.00 **Plenary Farewell**

13.00 – 14.30 **Lunch**

Giotto

Galileo

Carraresi

Petrarca

Mantegna 1

Mantegna 2

Palladio

Antenore

Giotto

Giotto

Keynote Presentations

Giotto Room

Kirsten Dunlop has been the Chief Executive Officer at Climate KIC since 2017, leading the organisation with a deep conviction in our capacity to learn and evolve into a climate-resilient society. She brings over 30 years of experience catalysing systemic transformations in a career spanning academia, consulting, banking, and insurance. Kirsten serves on various Advisory Boards and is a recognized leader at the European Commission Economic and Societal Impact of Research and Innovation (ESIR) expert group.

14.30 – 14.45**Carbon Farming: A Pathway to Sustainable Competitiveness**

Alessandra Zampieri has been the Director of the Directorate for Sustainable Resources of the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC) since October 2022. As the science and knowledge service of the European Commission, the JRC's mission is to support EU policies with independent evidence throughout the whole policy cycle. Alessandra's career started in Brussels, where she joined the European Commission immediately after graduating in Economics from the University of Genoa.

14.45 – 15.00**The Journey of a Project Developer**

Francesco Musardo is CEO and Co-Founder of Radica (formerly Alberami), Italy's pioneering climate-tech company in agricultural carbon markets. He developed the country's first ICROA-endorsed carbon farming project, managing 500+ farmers and delivering compliance-grade carbon removal credits. With 20+ years in international finance and sustainability, Francesco bridges climate science, regulatory frameworks, and market innovation across Mediterranean agriculture.

Keynote Presentations

Giotto Room

Wednesday 18th

9.00 – 9.45

Soil Monitoring Directive Implementation and Carbon Farming

Mirco Barbero is policy officer in soil protection and sustainable land use; he leads the Soil Team since June 2019 within the Unit Land use and management, Directorate-General Environment, European Commission. Mirco has a degree in physics and has worked for a dozen of years in the private sector as responsible for the quality assurance of products and services. He joined the Commission in 2005 where he worked mainly as team leader in internal audit, advising the management on how to improve performance, governance and risk management in several policy areas. He and his team have prepared the EU Soil Strategy and the proposal for the EU Soil Monitoring and Resilience Directive, negotiating it with the European Parliament and Council.

9.00 – 9.45

The Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe'

Marianna Paolino is an experienced EU policy officer with over 15 years of service in the European Commission. She currently works in the Directorate-General for Agriculture and Rural Development (DG AGRI) as a programme officer in Unit F2 – Research and Innovation, where she is responsible for Horizon activities on climate smart agriculture. Marianna is also part of the Mission Soil Secretariat team. Her multidisciplinary background in agronomy, biotechnology, and biochemistry is complemented by extensive experience in policy development on organic trade, food safety, and sustainability. Throughout her career, Marianna has played key roles in shaping EU policies and legislation on plant protection products and organic production, contributing to the achievement of the EU's Green Deal and sustainability objectives. She holds a PhD in Biochemistry, Cellular and Molecular Biology.

9.00 – 9.45

State of Play and Next Steps for Carbon Farming Certification in the EU

Valeria Forlin is the Deputy Head of Unit for Land Economy and Carbon Removals, at the European Commission's Directorate-General for Climate Action, where she is specialised in the land sector's pivotal role in combating climate change. Her work focuses on reducing agricultural emissions, enhancing carbon sinks in soils and forests. With a background in environmental economics, she previously contributed to European space policies at UCLouvain and worked extensively in microeconomics, industrial organization, and public economics.

14.30 – 14.50

Providing High-Quality Data and Developing Risk Assessment for Carbon Removals

Panos Panagos is the project leader of the EU Soil Observatory (EUSO). Panos has a PhD in soil erosion modelling from University of Basel, and Master in Business Administration from Patras University and an Information Technology degree from Athens University of Economics & Business. Panos lead the European and Global soil erosion assessments and contributes to modelling assessments of soil organic carbon, diffuse pollution and nutrients in soil.

Plenary Session 1

Giotto Room

[YouTube](#)

Carbon Farming for Climate Mitigation, Biodiversity and Sustainable Agriculture and Forestry

Carbon farming represents an opportunity to support the transition to more sustainable land uses. This high-level policy session focuses on the efforts made by the European Commission to align climate targets and farmers and foresters' aspirations.

Session Organisers

Saskia Keesstra (Climate KIC) and Sonia Pietosi (EIT Food)

Panel Session Moderator

Dr. Saskia Keesstra is Senior Researcher Sustainable land and water management at Climate KIC with a background in Physical Geography. She also part-time works at Wageningen Environmental Research. She works on finding nature-based solutions in a socio-economic sustainable system to facilitate the transition towards climate neutral and resilient regions on topics like soil, climate adaptation and water management; specifically in the agri-food system and forestry. She is also one of the main organisers of the Carbon Farming Summits.

Invited Panellists

Kurt Vandenberghe has been the Director-General for Climate Action (DG CLIMA) at the European Commission since January 2023. Before that, he acted as the Green Deal and Health advisor to President Ursula von der Leyen, Director for Policy & Programming of DG Research and Innovation, and Acting Director for Research & Innovation Outreach. Kurt holds degrees in Public and International Affairs and International Relations from Universities in Belgium, Italy and the US.

Elisabeth Werner has been the Director-General for Agriculture and Rural Development (DG AGRI) at the European Commission since May 2025. With almost 30 years of experience within the European Commission, Elisabeth brings a strong combination of institutional knowledge, budgetary expertise and coordination skills across a wide range of policy areas. Her background includes extensive work on a number of policy dossiers, including land transport, competitiveness, clean industry and sustainability. Elisabeth holds degrees in Economics and European Affairs.

Massimiliano Giansanti, born in Rome, president of Confagricoltura (General Confederation of Italian Agriculture), has also been president of COPA (Committee of Professional Agricultural Organizations of the European Union) since September 2024. He is president of Agricola Giansanti srl and CEO of the Di Muzio Agricultural Group, which operates in the provinces of Rome, Viterbo, and Parma, companies specialize in the production of cereals, kiwis, milk, and livestock products, that are active in the agro-industrial and agro-energy sectors through the production of electricity and photovoltaic energy. He also produces Parmigiano Reggiano cheese in Parma and high-quality cow's milk for the Centrale del Latte di Roma.

Rémi Rocca has been serving as the Global Vice President of Sustainability for Royal Canin at Mars since January 2025. Prior to joining Mars, Rémi held senior leadership roles at McDonald's in both France and the United States. Most recently, he served as Senior Director of Impact, overseeing Corporate Communications, Public Affairs, ESG, and Philanthropy. During his tenure, he led transformative programs including the establishment of a Global Regenerative Agriculture Platform, and significant advancements in carbon emissions reduction.

Plenary Session 2

Giotto Room

YouTube

Financing the Transition: Current Trends and Emerging Opportunities

The voluntary demand for soil carbon credits, at the price needed to unlock change, is still not sufficient to enable a quick roll out of carbon farming across the EU. This multi-actor session explores current trends and potential solutions for directing resources towards carbon markets and corporate actions.

Session Organiser **Tristano Bacchetti De Gregoris (SAE Innova)**

Panel Session Moderator

Giulia Stellari is a Managing Director at Fall Line Capital, leading impact initiatives in farmland and venture portfolios. Previously at Unilever, she managed global sustainable procurement programs, advancing digital agriculture, transparency, and greenhouse gas reduction programs. She co-founded AgSquared, a farm data management platform, and holds a Ph.D. in Plant Molecular Biology from Cornell and an A.B. in biology from Harvard. Giulia is also a non-executive director at SIPEF, Chair of Cool Farm Alliance, former member of the SBTi Technical Advisory Group, advisor to UNHCR on carbon removals, and an expert on the EU Expert Group on Carbon Removals.

Invited Panellists

Gabriella Cevallos is a manager within the agrifood team at Deloitte Sustainability France. She has worked over the years on carbon accounting for the agricultural and forestry sectors, helping to design decarbonization or regenerative agriculture strategies for the agrifood sector, as well as in engaging suppliers to support decarbonization and strengthening the resilience of value chains.

Hugh McDonald is a Senior Fellow at Ecologic Institute, where he coordinates the economics team. An environmental economist, he researches and advises on policies to promote carbon removals, reduce agricultural emissions, and finance biodiversity. His work on carbon farming includes publications for the European Commission's DG CLIMA, the European Parliament, and the German Environment Agency, among others, as well as support to the European Scientific Advisory Board on Climate Change.

Christian Holzleitner is Head of Unit responsible for Land economy and Carbon removals at the European Commission's Directorate-General for Climate Action. Previously, he worked as Head of Unit for Finance for Innovation and Land Use and assistant to the Director-General for Climate Action covering all issues related to EU and international climate policy; and at the Directorate-General for Competition in the area of State aid for services of general economic interest in the postal, transport, and health sectors. Christian is an economist and holds a PhD from the University of Linz (Austria).

Chris Adamo is head of Global Sustainability Impact & B Corp, assisting Danone to create social and environmental impact throughout its business as a certified B Corp. Chris helps Danone build sustainability strategies and policies to implement its Danone Impact Journey. Prior to joining Danone, Chris spent over a decade in the U.S. government leading strategies on agriculture, natural resources, and climate change. He served as chief of staff for the White House Council on Environmental Quality under President Barack Obama and led the Senate Committee on Agriculture, Nutrition and Forestry.

Gerdus van der Laarse is a systemic finance strategist at Metabolic, a systems change organization that supports bioregional transitions to a circular, regenerative economy. With a multidisciplinary background in engineering, policy, and finance, he focuses on orchestrating capital for large-scale systems change. His work includes designing capital orchestration approaches that enable regenerative agricultural practices, scaling decarbonization technologies in the agrifood sector, and shaping regional transition strategies. By connecting financial, policy, and industry actors, he helps turn systemic transition plans into investable action.

Plenary Session 3

Giotto Room

YouTube

Common Objectives: Carbon Farming for Everyone?

While carbon farming is a relatively new concept, movements working towards more sustainable agricultural practices are not. This session brings together representatives of young farmers, and organic, regenerative, and climate smart agriculture, to explore the synergies and tensions between the objectives and methods of carbon farming and the goals and approaches of these movements.

Session Organisers **Mathieu Mal (EEB) and Kaj Granholm (BSAG)**

Panel Session Moderator

Mathieu Mal works at the European Environmental Bureau (EEB), Europe's largest network of environmental citizens' organisations, where he leads the policy work and strategy on the intersections between agriculture and climate. He coordinates the policy work in the CREDIBLE carbon farming project, co-leads the climate work of the EU Food Policy Coalition, and is a member of the EU Commission's Expert Group on Carbon Removals.

Invited Panellists

Martina Dal Grande is a winegrower based in the Conegliano Valdobbiadene wine region. For the past seven years she has been managing her vineyards, implementing regenerative agriculture practices. She is a member of ANGA, the youth association of Confagricoltura, for which she served as a delegate to CEJA, the European Council of Young Farmers. Her work focuses on knowledge dissemination and sharing of best practices in agriculture, based on the belief that continuous training, practical field experience, and the systematic analysis of results represent the pathway to achieving tangible outcomes.

Marco Paravicini Crespi is a biodynamic farmer and owner of Cascine Orsine Farm in Bereguardo. He brings over ten years of experience in the organic retail and distribution sector with EcorNaturasi. He currently serves as Vice President of FederBio, the Italian federation for organic and biodynamic agriculture.

Peter Fröhlich is a farmer, agronomist, and entrepreneur with over 20 years of experience driving agricultural innovation. A founding member of EARA and a prominent voice in European regenerative farming. Peter has spent the past decade advancing data interoperability, precision agriculture, and digital agronomy. His work now converges in AgriPurpose, a leading approval framework for Regenerative Agriculture.

Ivano Assenza is a Carbon Markets Specialist at the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), working at the intersection of carbon finance, climate-smart agriculture and nature-based solutions in European and international policy frameworks. His work focuses on ensuring that carbon markets contribute to resilient agrifood systems, deliver measurable climate outcomes, strengthen farmer livelihoods and generate co-benefits such as soil health, biodiversity and ecosystem restoration.

Plenary Session 4

Giotto Room

YouTube

Managing Risk in Carbon Farming: Uncertainties, MRV, Liabilities, and Insurance

Managing risk is central in carbon farming, as uncertainty in MRV systems, liability for reversals and project failures, and evolving financial and insurance mechanisms directly shape environmental credibility and market viability. This session will unpack how these factors are handled across the carbon/agricultural value chain—from measurement to finance and implementation—and explore how insurance and adaptive management can make climate projects more resilient and trustworthy.

Session Organiser Hannes Mollenhauer (UFZ)

Panel Session Moderator

Hannes Mollenhauer is a researcher at the Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research (UFZ), working at the interface of climate action and land-use management. His work focuses on carbon farming and climate-smart agriculture, with particular attention to drought stress prediction, risk management, and MRV (monitoring, reporting and verification). He supports science-to-policy exchange and stakeholder dialogue.

Invited Panellists

Alexa Mayer-Bosse leads Nature-based Risk Solutions at Munich Re. As a senior underwriter in agriculture, forestry, carbon, and parametric insurance, she specializes in assessing production risks and structuring risk-transfer solutions. Her work leverages advanced remote-sensing technologies. She holds an MBA in finance, marketing and ICT and is an active family farmer.

Francesco Morari is professor of soil and water conservation and soil physics at the University of Padova, Italy. He is also adjunct Professor at the Crop & Soil Department, University of Georgia, USA. He is the director of the Experimental Farm of the University of Padova and his major research interests are on soil mapping and precision agriculture, sustainability of agricultural systems and soil physics, and GHGs monitoring and mitigation.

Anastasia Volkova is a visionary leader shaping the category of agricultural resilience. She has more than a decade of experience in academia and business, creating innovative software solutions. Anastasia holds a Ph.D. in aerospace engineering and has been named a 2023 UBS Global Visionary, one of BBC's "Top 100 Women" and is on the TIME100 Next list.

Constantinos Hatziparadisis is a Greek farmer based in Northern Greece and runs the Hatziparadisis farm. He is associated with modern, lower-impact cultivation methods such as conservation agriculture and reduced tillage, and has experience with practices aimed at cutting the carbon footprint of crop production. He has also been involved in EU sustainability and innovation initiatives in agriculture. In the LILAS4SOILS context, he is connected to the project's Living Labs approach supporting carbon-farming adoption in Greece (GRECFI²).

Dr. Ana Gonzalez Pelaez is Head of Agroecosystems at PlanetaryX, focused on scaling nature and credit markets for regenerative agriculture. She grew up on a farm in Spain and has dedicated her career to international economic development, agriculture and climate risk finance, holding senior roles across the public and private sectors, academia and international partnerships. Most recently, she co-led the European Commission and European Investment Bank publication quantifying the climate risks to EU-27 agriculture and insurance systems. She is a 2026 Awardee of the Fin-Erth Women in Climate Awards (Agriculture).

Plenary Session 5

Giotto Room

YouTube

The Next Steps for Carbon Farming – Broadening Beyond Agriculture

This session will explore the future of carbon farming as a key instrument for promoting sustainable land and resource use across multiple sectors. While carbon farming has traditionally been associated with agriculture, this discussion will broaden the perspective to include its applications and opportunities in forestry, biodiversity, and the bioeconomy value chain as a whole. It will discuss and compare the market development constraints and perspectives in these different sectors. The way CRCF will/could help support the broad objective of increasing the LULUCF carbon sink will also be addressed.

Session Organiser Daniel Zimmer (Climate KIC)

Panel Session Moderator

Dr. Daniel Zimmer has an engineering and hydrology background and is leading the Sustainable Land Use activities at Climate KIC. He is also one of the main architects of the European Carbon Farming Summits and is co-leading the Finance Design Team of the 1000 Landscapes for 1 Billion people initiative. He has been before the Chief Executive of the World Water Council where he developed a global experience on water-related issues spanning from research & engineering to finance and geopolitics.

Invited Panellists

Lucia Perugini is an expert on carbon farming certification and LULUCF at the European Environment Agency. With a PhD in forest ecology, her background spans forestry and climate change science. Previously at CMCC Italy, she contributed to major EU research projects and served for 15 years as Italy's UNFCCC delegate on CDM, LULUCF, agriculture, and REDD+.

Anneli Lundmark is CEO of Nordiskt Naturkapital (Nordic Nature Capital) with extensive experience in developing and commercialising new business models across the forest value chain. She acts as a key connector between landowners, buyers and policymakers, translating carbon forestry frameworks into investable projects and real buyer demand. She currently focuses on project development and the sale of high-quality carbon credits in the Nordic region.

Anna Uebachs is a Senior Carbon Project Developer at aeco GmbH with an interdisciplinary background in natural and social sciences. They have extensive experience developing carbon projects and methodologies across a range of project types. At aeco, they currently focus on scaling peatland rewetting by combining hands-on field experience, farm-level stakeholder engagement with the practical requirements of carbon finance.

John Brosnan joined the Irish Co-operative Organisation Society (ICOS) in June 2022 in the newly-created post of Bioeconomy Executive, working primarily on advancing co-operative involvement in the growing and evolving Bioeconomy. John has been working in the agri-food sector for over 20 years, beginning in the food service sector before moving on to work for farmer-owned farm services co-operative, FRS for 16 years in project and operations management. This included agri-environmental and sustainability services provided directly to farmers on behalf of Irish state and semi-state bodies.

Tomas Lundmark is Professor Emeritus of Silviculture and has more than 40 years of experience in forest research, policy, and sustainable land management. He is also an active forest owner, bringing a practical perspective on how carbon removals can be implemented in real-world forestry. Today, he is CEO of Carbon Capture Company, where he works on developing high-integrity standards and certification systems for forest carbon removals aligned with the EU Carbon Removal Carbon Farming regulation (CRCF). Lundmark has contributed to expert and focus group processes supporting the design and implementation of CRCF methodologies and has extensive networks across forest owners, industry, public authorities, and EU institutions.

Christian Holzleitner is Head of Unit responsible for Land economy and Carbon removals at the European Commission's Directorate-General for Climate Action. Previously, he worked as Head of Unit for Finance for Innovation and Land Use and assistant to the Director-General for Climate Action covering all issues related to EU and international climate policy; and at the Directorate-General for Competition in the area of State aid for services of general economic interest in the postal, transport, and health sectors. Christian is an economist and holds a PhD from the University of Linz (Austria).

Parallel Sessions 1 – Tuesday 17th - 11.30 – 13.00

A. FROM PRACTICE TO IMPACT

• A1. Giving Voice to Farmers: From Practice to Proof in Carbon Farming

Keywords: Farmers' voices; Carbon farming practices; MRV and certification; Communities of practice; Demonstration farms; Soil health; Farm resilience; Co-benefits.

This session puts farmers at the centre of carbon farming discussions, drawing directly on their experiences across diverse European initiatives. Farmers share why they engage in carbon farming, how practices are implemented on-farm, and the challenges they encounter in achieving measurable outcomes. The discussion covers soil health, emissions reduction, carbon sequestration, farm resilience, and the real economic, environmental, and social impacts observed in practice. A strong focus is placed on farmers' experiences with MRV, certification schemes, advisory services, and digital tools. The session also highlights the role of demonstration farms, peer-to-peer learning, and communities of practice in building trust and long-term engagement. By grounding policy and project design in real farm-level realities, the session aims to support more inclusive, scalable carbon farming strategies.

Main contributors: Image Line srl, Teagasc, Farm Carbon Toolkit.

Mantegna 1 Room

[YouTube](#)

• A2. Improved Forest Management and Community-Led Carbon Forestry: From CRCF Integration to Investment Feasibility and MRV Innovation

Keywords: Improved Forest Management, Communities, Forest Carbon Credits, CRCF, MRV.

This session explores how Improved Forest Management (IFM) and community-led forest carbon initiatives can deliver credible removals under the CRCF and evolving LULUCF policies. It combines practical IFM project experience with economic analysis of forest carbon investments and innovation in MRV systems. Case studies from Italy and Nordic countries illustrate baseline choices, risk management, profitability, and the use of digital tools such as living labs and forest digital twins. By integrating project development, finance, and monitoring perspectives, the session provides actionable insights for scaling inclusive, cost-effective, and scientifically robust forest carbon farming across diverse European contexts.

Main contributors: I4CE, Council for Research in Agriculture and Analysis of Agricultural Economics, Research Centre Policies and Bioeconomy, Natural Resources Institute Finland.

Carraresi Room

[YouTube](#)

• A3. From Ambition to Action: Adaptive Governance Systems Supporting Smart and Inclusive Carbon Farming

Keywords: Adaptive Governance, Smart Carbon Farming, Complex (Eco)Systems Dynamics, CRCF, Climate Justice, Policy Innovation, Quintuple Helix Collaboration Framework, Environmental Governance, Social equity and Sustainable Development, ISO 14064-2, MRV framework, Regions, Farmer-centric, Carbon Commons.

This interactive workshop develops a shared governance roadmap for Smart Carbon Farming using adaptive, learning-oriented approaches. Drawing on experience from multiple EU projects and countries, participants explore how governance systems can better integrate policy, markets, and local practice while addressing complexity, climate justice, and stakeholder trust. Structured around four lenses—adaptive governance, farmers' perspectives, regional institutions, and carbon commons—the session uses a World Café format to co-create actionable governance principles and solutions. Outcomes include practical guidance for policymakers, farmers, market actors, and regional agencies, supporting inclusive, climate-resilient carbon farming systems that align with CRCF objectives and regional realities.

Main contributors: Hanze University of Applied Sciences, Agroparistech, Carbonica project, Smart Carbon Farming (Interreg), Oost NL, The Good Ones AG (tgo AG).

Palladio Room

B. THINKING BEYOND CARBON

- **B1. Beyond Carbon: Integrating Environmental, Social, and Economic Co-Benefits into Land Use, Business, and Markets**

Keywords: climate-neutral, sustainable transition, environmental, social and economic co-benefits, land-use strategies, natural capital, MRV frameworks, nature-based solutions, business strategy, governance.

This workshop explores how land-use systems can deliver climate mitigation alongside environmental, social, and economic co-benefits. Participants examine how co-benefits such as biodiversity, natural capital, social value, and climate resilience can be financed, governed, and verified. The session connects farm-level practices with land-use strategies, business decision-making, and outcome-based MRV frameworks. Through practical examples and open discussion, the workshop highlights how governance, business innovation, MRV, and finance can work together to scale regenerative and nature-based solutions across Europe, ensuring that climate-neutral transitions also deliver tangible benefits for communities and ecosystems.

Main contributors: LandShift project (GA: 101182007), CONSULAI.

Donatello Room

C. STANDARDS, POLICY, AND OWNERSHIP RIGHTS

- **C1. Integrating the CRCF into International MRV Systems and the Global Climate Action Agenda**

Keywords: Value Chain Integration, Advanced MRV systems, Data and Reporting consistency, Science-based policy.

This session examines how the EU Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF) can be aligned with international MRV systems and global climate reporting. Panelists explore how CRCF data and methodologies could support national climate targets, NDCs, and broader public objectives such as soil health and farm income. Key challenges discussed include data interoperability, ownership, avoidance of double counting, and coordination across national, European, and global levels. Drawing on national experiences and international initiatives, the session highlights scientific, technical, and policy requirements for scaling CRCF beyond Europe. Interactive audience engagement will help identify opportunities to strengthen trust, coherence, and integrity across the full value chain from data collection to policy implementation.

Main contributors: Emissierechten.nl, International "4 per 1000" Initiative, Directorate of Climate Change Republic of Türkiye, CREA, ICOS ERIC, Soil Carbon Futures, INRAE.

Galileo Room

[YouTube](#)

D. FINANCING CARBON FARMING AT SCALE

• D1. From Verified Claims to Scaled Action: Building the European Infrastructure for Scope 3 Carbon Farming.

Keywords: GHG emissions, Scope 3, insetting, interoperable standards, scale.

Scope 3 emission reductions and removals from agriculture are increasingly critical for corporate climate targets, yet Europe lacks a recognised validation and verification infrastructure for supply-chain insetting. This session examines why proven on-farm interventions—such as soil management, fertiliser efficiency, and agroforestry—struggle to scale into credible Scope 3 claims. Panelists explore gaps between corporate reporting requirements and existing regulatory support, creating uncertainty for both companies and farmers. The discussion highlights emerging solutions, including landscape-level collaboration, interoperable MRV systems, blended finance models, and supply-chain approaches. The session concludes with a debate on the role of EU policy in enabling standardised, affordable MRV and fostering partnerships needed to scale carbon farming while ensuring integrity, additionality, and alignment with climate objectives.

Main contributors: EIT Food, Proba, KPMG Iceland, Agricarbon, Institute of Agrifood Research and Technology (IRTA), EOS Data Analytics.

Giotto Room

[YouTube](#)

• D2. From Farm to Value Chain: Scaling Regenerative Agriculture through Collaboration, Finance, and Certification

Keywords: Regenerative Agriculture, Value chain, MRV, Finance, Co-benefits.

This panel explores how regenerative agriculture and carbon farming can move from pilot projects to mainstream adoption by aligning actors across the value chain. Drawing on large-scale initiatives, panelists discuss farmer-centred programmes, corporate supply-chain strategies, innovative financing mechanisms, and evolving certification frameworks. Topics include creating financial incentives for farmers, embedding regenerative practices beyond carbon alone, lowering barriers through insetting and ecosystem service payments, and building trust through credible MRV aligned with emerging EU frameworks. By integrating perspectives from farmers, corporates, finance, and certification bodies, the session illustrates how collaboration, investment, and verification can jointly support climate impact, resilient supply chains, and scalable regenerative agriculture across Europe.

Main contributors: VIVESCIA, Biospheres, ClimatePal, Social Carbon Foundation, Flemish Action Platform Carbon Removal & Carbon Farming.

Mantegna 2 Room

[YouTube](#)

E. BUILDING ROBUST AND FLEXIBLE MRV

- **E1. Data and Approaches for Consistent Quantification of Emissions and Removals in Baseline and Carbon Farming Activities**

This session focuses on methodological and data challenges in quantifying emissions and removals under the EU Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming Regulation (CRCF). It examines how different baseline approaches—static or dynamic, project-specific or standardised—affect the calculation of net carbon benefits. Through case studies in agricultural and forest systems, speakers present consistent frameworks for linking carbon fluxes to farming activities at field and regional levels. Emphasis is placed on high-granularity activity data, modelling and hybrid approaches, and best practices for operational MRV. The session brings together scientists, policymakers, service providers, and certification actors to identify scalable, transparent, and robust methods for baseline definition and carbon accounting.

Main contributors: Joint Research Centre - European Commission, BETA tech centre, University of Vic - Central University of Catalonia, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Horta Srl, University of Padova.

Petrarca Room

[YouTube](#)

- **E2. From Pilots to Practice: Building a Fair, Farmer-Empowered Carbon Registry for Europe**

Keywords: Carbon removals, Carbon Farming, CRCF, MRV, Carbon registry.

Europe is moving fast from carbon farming pilots to real-world implementation — but trust, usability, and transparency will determine success. This interactive workshop brings together insights from the Open Geospatial Carbon Registry (OGCR) and CAFAMORE project to explore how farmer-empowered MRV and registry design can enable CRCF-aligned, credible markets. Participants will help shape the next generation of European carbon registry by sharing real user needs, pain points, and success factors — from the farmer's field to market-level transparency. This session will be particularly valuable for small and commercial farmers, policy-makers, agri-businesses focusing on supply chain empowerment and carbon project developers.

Main contributors: thriveGEO GmbH, Agrosolutions.

Antenore Room

Parallel Sessions 2 – Tuesday 17th - 16.15 – 17.45

A. FROM PRACTICE TO IMPACT

• A4. Climate-Smart and Resilient Agrifood Systems Through Industry Frameworks and Robust Data Infrastructure

Keywords: Climate-smart agriculture, regenerative agriculture, agri-food value chain, data, data infrastructures, farm level.

This session explores how climate-smart and regenerative agriculture can scale across agrifood value chains through aligned industry frameworks and robust data infrastructures. Introductory presentations and a panel discussion address how farm-level practices connect to industry criteria, value-chain data flows, and policy and corporate reporting requirements. Panelists discuss challenges related to measuring impact at farm, crop, and product levels, aligning industry frameworks with farmer needs, and contributing to policy and corporate KPIs. Particular attention is given to data management infrastructures that support interoperability and the principle of “collect once, use many times.” The session offers insights into how coordinated data approaches can support resilience, climate mitigation, and lasting positive impact across agrifood systems.

Main contributors: Baltic Sea Action Group (BSAG), BAT Agrar GmbH & Co. KG: CO2NSERVE, Permarobotics GmbH.

Mantegna 2 Room

[YouTube](#)

• A5. Enabling Carbon Farming at Farm Level

Keywords: Practical examples, agriculture, enablers.

This session creates an open dialogue on the factors that enable or hinder farmers' adoption of carbon farming practices. Farmers and farmer representatives share practical experiences, highlighting motivations, opportunities, and structural barriers encountered in implementation. The discussion addresses operational challenges, market conditions, technology and innovation support, and lessons learned from real-world practice placing the farmer's voice at the centre of the transition.

Main contributors: Confagricoltura Veneto, EIT Food/LILAS4SOILS project.

Galileo Room

[YouTube](#)

• A6. From Soil Practice to Climate Impact: Turning Knowledge into Scalable Action

Keywords: farmer-led validation, credible MRV, holistic soil health, Cross country collaboration.

This interactive workshop addresses the gap between soil research, on-farm practice, and scalable climate impact. It explores why many initiatives struggle to scale due to narrow metrics, lack of farmer-centred design, or weak pathways from knowledge to implementation. Through short pitches and structured roundtable discussions, participants examine how soil practices can be translated into measurable outcomes, credible MRV, policy uptake, and market readiness. The session emphasises holistic soil health perspectives that integrate carbon, nutrients, biology, and resilience, and concludes with a synthesis of priority actions to accelerate soil-based climate impact.

Main contributors: Climate KIC/ Soil Innovation Partnership, innomine, Eurofins.

Palladio Room

B. THINKING BEYOND CARBON

- **B2. Beyond the Farm Gate: Scaling up Carbon Interventions and Regenerative Agriculture to the Landscape Level**

Keywords: Landscape approaches, Regenerative agriculture, Carbon co-benefits, Governance, Monitoring & Evaluation, Biodiversity, Climate resilience, Sustainable value chains, Finance.

This session explores how carbon farming and regenerative agriculture can be implemented, measured, and financed at landscape scale. Building on practical examples, participants examine barriers and enablers of collective action, including farmer engagement, trust-building, and alignment with corporate and financing requirements. The session discusses how carbon outcomes can be integrated with biodiversity and community co-benefits using landscape-level measurement frameworks, and how carbon can act as a financing lever through offsetting, insetting, and blended finance. Participants gain insights into the links between governance, measurement, and finance in designing effective landscape-scale initiatives.

Main contributors: LandScale / Rainforest Alliance, BIOSPHERES, 3Keel.

Donatello Room

C. STANDARDS, POLICY, AND OWNERSHIP RIGHTS

- **C2. Demystifying Carbon Forestry: Forests vs. Agriculture? Spot the Difference and Lessons for an EU-Ready Land Use Policy**

Keywords: Market, carbon pathways, removals, value-chain, circular economy.

This session addresses common myths and misconceptions surrounding carbon forestry and agricultural carbon farming. It compares the two approaches in terms of baselines, permanence, measurability, and value creation, recognising that forestry and agriculture operate under different business and biological logics. The discussion focuses on integrity, fit-for-purpose MRV, leakage control, and aligned incentives, while examining how mechanisms such as CRCF and CSRD can support coherence across land-use pathways. By moving from competition to complementarity, the session aims to translate current theory and regulation into practical, cross-sector policy recommendations.

Main contributors: Carbon Capture Company AB.

Antenore Room

D. FINANCING CARBON FARMING AT SCALE

• D3. Scaling Credible Carbon Farming: Harmonized Measurement, Public Financing, Offset Buyers, and Co-Claiming Across the Value Chain

Keywords: Supply chain, offset buyers, integrity, transparency, farmer-centric, robustness, third-party verified.

This panel explores how carbon farming and regenerative agriculture projects can unlock increased and more diverse financing while maintaining environmental integrity. It focuses on financing models involving multiple actors—such as insetting and offset buyers alongside private and institutional investors—within single projects. Panelists examine how robust measurement, accounting, monitoring and verification enable co-claiming of climate benefits without double counting, and how these approaches align with international frameworks such as the GHG Land Sector Guidance and the SBTi Corporate Net-Zero Standard. Drawing on practical project experience, independent verification perspectives, supply-chain realities, and scientific research, the discussion clarifies current challenges, emerging best practices, and remaining gaps. The session aims to provide insights into how credible carbon farming initiatives can scale, attract blended finance, and deliver measurable climate, nature, and value-chain benefits for farmers, buyers, and investors.

Main contributors: Soil Capital, ReGeneration, SustainCERT, Harper Adams University.

Giotto Room

[YouTube](#)

• D4. Bridging Finance Streams for the Agricultural Transition: Co-Claiming of Carbon Benefits and Complementarity Between Carbon and Biodiversity Approaches in Agricultural Value Chains

Keywords: Finance streams, carbon farming, carbon markets, biodiversity co-benefits, co-claiming, agri-food sector perspective.

This session examines how the agricultural transition can be financed through a combination of public incentives, voluntary and compliance carbon markets, private investment, and emerging biodiversity approaches. It addresses challenges related to co-claiming environmental benefits, preventing double counting, and integrating climate mitigation and biodiversity outcomes at farm level. Starting from a conceptual overview of funding streams, the session then presents practical experiences from a French farmers' cooperative and integrated monitoring tools linking carbon sequestration and biodiversity outcomes. A concluding roundtable with agrifood companies explores private-sector readiness to finance biodiversity co-benefits and the role of carbon farming frameworks in recognising and rewarding them.

Main contributors: Agrosolutions, I4CE, Ecologic Institute, Mars Company.

Carraresi Room

[YouTube](#)

E. BUILDING ROBUST AND FLEXIBLE MRV

• E3. Making It Count: Monitoring And Certification Approaches For Forest Carbon Projects and Forestry Landscapes

Keywords: Resilience, carbon removals, carbon forestry, baselines, MRV, certification, use cases.

High-integrity forest carbon farming under the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Framework (CRCF) depends on robust monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV), defensible baselines, and credible certification approaches. Good carbon credits are a complex undertaking considering the diverse landscapes of the EU, and last but not least their potential use cases. This session aims for a comprehensive look at the challenges ahead as it brings together research institutes, tool developers, technology providers, certification actors, and practitioners from the Union and beyond to explore how forest and landscape carbon projects can be measured, validated, and ultimately also communicated credibly and at scale for those in the field but also for policymakers, buyers, and the general public.

Main contributors: Agri-Food and Biosciences Institute, CREA - Forestry and Wood, OXO Earth Technologies GmbH, Caritas Austria, PEFC Italy.

Mantegna 1 Room

[YouTube](#)

• E4. Data and Approaches for Consistent Quantification of Emissions and Removals in Baseline and Carbon Farming Activities

This session focuses on methodological and data challenges in quantifying emissions and removals under the EU Carbon Removal and Carbon Farming Regulation (CRCF). It examines how different baseline approaches—static or dynamic, project-specific or standardised—affect the calculation of net carbon benefits. Through case studies in agricultural and forest systems, speakers present consistent frameworks for linking carbon fluxes to farming activities at field and regional levels. Emphasis is placed on high-granularity activity data, modelling and hybrid approaches, and best practices for operational MRV. The session brings together scientists, policymakers, service providers, and certification actors to identify scalable, transparent, and robust methods for baseline definition and carbon accounting.

Main contributors: Joint Research Centre - European Commission, Regrow Ag, GeoVille GmbH, Università degli studi di Milano, Finnish Meteorological Institute.

Petrarca Room

[YouTube](#)

Parallel Sessions 3 – Wednesday 18th - 11.30 – 13.00

A. FROM PRACTICE TO IMPACT

• A7. Carbon Farming in Practice: Lessons from BASF's EU Projects and their applicability to CRCF

Keywords: Carbon Farming Implementation, CRCF Implementation, Carbon Removals, MRV Digital Farming Tools, EU Carbon Farming Projects, Practical Case Studies, Scaling Sustainable Agriculture, Policy Implementation.

This session presents practical lessons from BASF's carbon farming projects implemented across the EU and examines their relevance for the Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF). It highlights end-to-end project delivery, from farmer engagement and digital farming tools to MRV and certification. Speakers reflect on implementation challenges, lessons learned, and opportunities to scale projects across diverse farming systems. Particular attention is given to the role of partnerships between farmers, project developers, value-chain actors and certification bodies, and how these collaborations support trust, consistency and scalability. The session also situates these experiences within EU climate policy objectives, demonstrating how carbon farming projects can support emission reductions, efficient input use, and sustainable agricultural practices while remaining accessible and practical for farmers.

Main contributors: BASF

Giotto Room

YouTube

• A8. Unlocking Synergies Among Agroforestry Actors Through Participatory Approaches

Keywords: Agroforestry systems Carbon removal and crediting Carbon modelling and assessment (e.g. LCA) Participatory approaches Multi-actor collaboration System design and innovation.

This workshop focuses on strengthening collaboration among agroforestry stakeholders to improve the role of agroforestry systems in carbon removal and carbon crediting under the Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF). The session will start with a brief participant introduction to identify backgrounds and expertise, followed by a system design approach to map key roles across the agroforestry value chain, including farmers, advisors, researchers, policymakers, and private-sector actors. Through participatory discussions, the workshop will explore the needs, expectations, and challenges of these actors in implementing and scaling up agroforestry systems. Particular attention will be given to strengthening connections and identifying synergies that enhance cooperation, knowledge exchange, and innovation. Drawing on experiences from Living Labs and EU projects such as AGROMIX, DigitAF, and REFOREST, participants will co-design context-specific solutions to overcome technical and administrative barriers. The outcomes will support a shared understanding of how collaboration, digital tools, and coordinated governance can advance agroforestry and its recognition within the CRCF framework.

Main contributors: University of Pisa, Italian Agroforestry Federation (AIAF), European Agroforestry Federation (EURAF), Polish Agroforestry Association, CREA, Research Centre Engineering and agro-food processing, Torino.

Palladio Room

B. THINKING BEYOND CARBON

• B3. How Smart Carbon Farming Can Build the Path for Agriculture in Wetlands

Keywords: Paludiculture, wetter agriculture, high water table peatlands, Smart Carbon Farming, emission avoidance, avoided emissions, carbon removals, MRV, CRCF, peat replacement, biochar, humus systems, governance, CAP integration, policy-ready carbon farming, biodiversity and water co-benefits.

This 90-minute participatory workshop explores how agriculture with high water levels on wetlands and peatlands can become a key pillar of Europe's climate mitigation strategy. Framed around the concept of Smart Carbon Farming, the session examines how wetter agricultural practices can significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions, enable additional carbon removals, and fit within the EU policy framework, while also questioning their economic viability. The workshop introduces the climate role of wetlands and peatlands and then engages participants in a role-play and World Café format, where they step into the role of a "smart carbon farmer" in 2045 managing drained peatlands. Guided by experts, participants rotate through thematic discussions on water-table management and emission avoidance, productive wetland use and value creation, additional carbon sequestration, and monitoring, reporting, and certification under the EU Carbon Removals and Carbon Farming Certification Framework (CRCF). The session concludes with reflections on the policy instruments, governance, and market frameworks needed to scale wetland carbon farming in Europe.

Main contributors: University of Greifswald, HumusGuru GmbH, Green Restoration, Ireland Co-operative Society Ltd, AC3A.

Donatello Room

• B5. Co-Benefits for Whom? Exploring Underlying Assumptions in the Design of an Intergenerational Open Geospatial Carbon Registry

Keywords: Co-benefits, Planetary boundaries, Intergenerational equity, Valuation of ecosystem services, Social and environmental justice.

This panel examines how carbon farming co-benefits—such as biodiversity, water regulation, livelihoods, and cultural value—are distributed across space and time, and how they are currently undervalued. The discussion focuses on who provides these benefits, who receives them, and whether existing carbon payment systems reflect this reality. Panelists question whether current valuation approaches align with long-term social and environmental outcomes and explore how CRCF could better support intergenerational equity. Rather than proposing a single solution, the session aims to surface assumptions and design choices that shape the delivery of co-benefits.

Main contributors: Opendeohub Foundation, ARC Zero, EURAF.

Mantegna 2 Room

[YouTube](#)

• B7. From Carbon to Carbon+Nature: Leveraging Existing Tools to Shape the Next Generation of Nature Credits

Keywords: Nature Credits, MRV, Carbon Farming, Agroecological Transition, Biodiversity Co-Benefits, Transaction Costs, Payments for Ecosystem Services.

This session explores how linking carbon farming with measurable biodiversity and ecosystem outcomes can strengthen credibility and reduce greenwashing risks. Using existing tools such as biodiversity units and payments for ecosystem services, speakers demonstrate how co-benefits can be recognised while highlighting trade-offs related to MRV complexity, transaction costs, and farmer engagement. The panel discusses how current approaches can inform the design of future Nature Credits that are simpler, scientifically credible, and aligned with real adoption on the ground.

Main contributors: Association of the Chambers of Agriculture of the Atlantic Area (AC3A), Fundación Global Nature, Chamber of Agriculture Pays de Loire, Chamber of Agriculture Normandy.

Galileo Room

[YouTube](#)

C. STANDARDS, POLICY, AND OWNERSHIP RIGHTS

• C3. Practical Implementation of Soil Carbon Projects

Keywords: Robustness, Transparency, MRV, Permanence, Long-term, VCM, International Standards / Methodologies.

This session provides an on-the-ground perspective on implementing high-integrity soil carbon projects within an evolving regulatory landscape. Panelists discuss operational challenges arising from CRCF requirements, voluntary carbon market standards, and international developments. Key topics include crediting periods, permanence, sampling costs, long-term farmer commitments, and methodological maturity. The discussion contrasts emerging regulatory expectations with practical experience from existing methodologies, highlighting risks of unnecessary duplication while maintaining integrity. The session advocates for harmonised, robust methodologies that can support climate integrity, market clarity, and scalability for farmers, project developers, and buyers.

Main contributors: Agreena, Agricarbon, ChrysaLabs, ReGeneration, Perennial, ReGrow, Seqana.

Petrarca Room

YouTube

E. BUILDING ROBUST AND FLEXIBLE MRV

• E5. Cost-Effectiveness: Harnessing State-of-the-Art Technology to Scale Viable Carbon Farming MRV

Keywords: Cost-benefit, MRV, Earth Observation, Proximal sensing.

This session explores how advanced technologies can address the cost–accuracy bottleneck in carbon farming MRV under the CRCF. Four technical innovations are presented, including optimised soil sampling and laboratory analysis, high-resolution Earth observation for plot-level monitoring, smart sampling strategies using optimisation algorithms, and hybrid in-situ sensing approaches. Together, these innovations demonstrate how uncertainty can be reduced while keeping MRV economically viable across different project scales and carbon prices. The second part of the session features a panel discussion on systemic barriers to scaling, particularly data access, interoperability, and the use of public datasets. The session provides evidence-based insights into how technology can support robust, scalable, and cost-effective MRV systems across Europe.

Main contributors: Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, ChrysaLabs, Agricarbon, CESBIO (CNRS, INRAe, CNES, IRD, Université de Toulouse), Climate KIC.

Mantegna 1 Room

YouTube

• E6. Data Sharing in Action: From Uncertainty to Trust in Carbon Farming MRV

Keywords: Data sharing, MRV Benchmarking, LTM, cross-sector conversation, Uncertainty Assessment.

This workshop brings together actors across the carbon farming value chain to improve data collection, sharing, and uncertainty management for robust and cost effective MRV consistent with the CRCF. We will examine how Long Term Monitoring (LTM) networks can support model calibration, MRV validation, and transparent uncertainty assessment. We will also discuss how scientific understanding of uncertainty can be translated into clear, scalable, and enforceable policy frameworks through standardized classification and quantification methods. The session begins with short success stories of data sharing and insights into uncertainty assessment, followed by interactive discussions on core questions: How can data sharing strategies deliver value for different actors? What uncertainty thresholds make projects viable? And how can complex MRV methodologies be simplified without compromising scientific rigor?

Main contributors: Flanders Research Institute for Agriculture, Fisheries and Food (ILVO), CinSOIL GmbH.

Antenore Room

INNOVATION SESSIONS

• F1. Innovation Session: Measurement, Verification, Certification, and Market Mechanisms

- Establishing Credible Claims: Defining Ownership and Transparency in Agricultural Carbon Removals (Regrow Ag).
- Reliable Carbon Credit Markets with Soil Carbon Scientific Centre (SCSC) (AGviser AG).
- Estimation of Carbon and Nitrogen Restitutions from Cover Crops Using Satellite Images for Supporting More Sustainable Agricultural Systems (Airbus Space Digital – Geospatial Business).
- Beyond Carbon: Fertilizing Livelihoods and Restoring Land in Global South Communities (Boomitra).
- Soil Fertility Improvement and Effects of Regenerative Practices on Organic Carbon Sequestration and Related Ecosystem Services in Kiwi Fruit Orchards of the Mediterranean Area (Agreement).
- Carbon Credit Fund (Innpact).
- Bringing Verified Scope 3 Claims to the Forefront of Decarbonisation Strategies (Agreena ApS).
- The Place of Carbon in Regenerative Agriculture: Aligning Carbon Farming with Ecosystem Regeneration (BIOSPHERES).
- Carbon Farming in Mediterranean Olive Groves: From Research to Market, Carbon Certification Pathways Through the LIFE. OLIVER project (Tetis Institute S.r.l.).
- LIFE ClimatePositive: Advancing carbon farming in forestry across Italy (Maria Giulia Pelosi).
- WOOD4LIFE: locking carbon, from forests to buildings (Giulia Cecchinato).
- Carbon Farming in Northern Peatlands - LIFE PeatCarbon Project (Pēteris Āboliņš).
- LIFE SUPER EU (İnga Kuze).
- Carbon Farming in Central Europe: Practical Experiences, Business Models, and Lessons from Two Years of Transnational Field Testing (Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation State Research Institute).

Main contributors: Klim GmbH, CarbonAI Limited, Regrow Ag, AGviser, AG, Airbus Space Digital – Geospatial business, Boomitra, Agreement, Innpact, Agreena ApS, BIOSPHERES, Tetis Institute S.r.l., Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation State Research Institute.

Carraresi Room

[YouTube](#)

Parallel Sessions 4 – Wednesday 18th - 16.15 – 17.45

B. THINKING BEYOND CARBON

• B4. Carbon Farming as a Public Good: Integrating Farmers, Consumers, and Policy

Keywords: Holistic evaluation, farm proficiency, fair rewards, beyond carbon.

The purpose of carbon markets in agriculture is to compensate farmers for increasing the amount of organic carbon in the soil, thereby helping to mitigate climate change. However, this objective may be hindered by various factors, and key farming organisations are advocating for improved monitoring, reporting and verification methods, as well as, evaluation approached incorporating indicators of farms' environmental, economic and social performance. This session will focus on evaluating and rewarding the positive environmental services provided by farming, beyond carbon sequestration and carbon markets, from the perspective of farmers. It will include four short talks and a interactive debate between the perspective speakers and attendees.

Main contributors: CREAM, Agri-Purpose AG, Agricultura regenerativa, Juntos Farm, SoilCO2.

Palladio Room

• B6. Carbon Farming Methodologies in Livestock

Keywords: Carbon farming, livestock, certification methodology, IED directive, CAP, innovative finance, methane reduction, emission reduction, technology.

This session examines certification methodologies for livestock carbon farming in the context of EU climate legislation, LULUCF targets, and the CRCF. It presents approaches to assessing methane and nitrous oxide emission reductions, links with CAP Strategic Plans, and synergies with EU environmental policies. The session also reviews methodologies adopted in different Member States and provides a SWOT analysis of challenges and opportunities facing livestock systems in the ecological transition.

Main contributors: Institut de l'élevage, Climate KIC, European Compost Network e.V. (ECN), OSI International Holding, Council for Research in Agriculture and Analysis of Agricultural Economics (CREA) – Policy and Bioeconomy Research Center.

Petrarca Room

[YouTube](#)

D. FINANCING CARBON FARMING AT SCALE

• D5. Building Public Trust in European Carbon Farming: Regulatory Support of Standards, Measurement, and Digital Infrastructure

This session explores how advanced technologies can address the cost-accuracy bottleneck in carbon farming MRV under the CRCF. Four technical innovations are presented, including optimised soil sampling and laboratory analysis, high-resolution Earth observation for plot-level monitoring, smart sampling strategies using optimisation algorithms, and hybrid in-situ sensing approaches. Together, these innovations demonstrate how uncertainty can be reduced while keeping MRV economically viable across different project scales and carbon prices. The second part of the session features a panel discussion on systemic barriers to scaling, particularly data access, interoperability, and the use of public datasets. The session provides evidence-based insights into how technology can support robust, scalable, and cost-effective MRV systems across Europe.

Main contributors: Seqana: European Commission DG CLIMA, Verra: RegenEarth, OpenGeoHub, Race2reduce, ARC Zero.

Mantegna 2 Room

[Youtube](#)

• D6. Innovative Financial Models to Scale Carbon Forestry

This session explores how carbon forestry can transition from pilot projects to bankable, large-scale solutions through innovative financial and business models. It examines insetting, public–private partnerships, blended finance, and ecosystem service certification as alternatives to traditional offsetting. Case studies illustrate emerging demand for high-integrity removals and the role of aggregators, long-term monitoring, and policy alignment in reducing investment risk. Investor perspectives address regulatory uncertainty, market fragmentation, and the need for clear EU frameworks. The session also highlights real-world reforestation and restoration projects, demonstrating how credible MRV and certification can connect ecological outcomes with sustainable finance and ESG reporting.

Main contributors: Etifor | Valuing Nature, Caritas of the Archdiocese of Vienna, Land Life Company, Arpinge Natural Capital, European Investment Bank, FSC International, EY Denkstatt.

Giotto Room

• D7. Unlocking European Small Farms' Access to Carbon Markets

Keywords: Small-scale farms, traceability, biodiversity, transparency, net zero, business model, Europe, local ecosystem, rural community.

Recent developments in the European Commission's Carbon Removal Certification Framework (2022–2024) have largely overlooked small-scale farms, creating a gap between EU carbon market mechanisms and on-the-ground farming realities. As a result, most European farms remain unable to benefit from climate transition incentives. This interactive workshop brings together farmers, buyers, platforms, public bodies, and researchers to explore how small farms can be effectively integrated into environmental markets in a way that is both financially viable and operationally feasible. Participants will work in small, stakeholder-focused groups to identify key barriers and co-create practical solutions. Discussions will address the financial viability of carbon markets for small farms, the quality and credibility of carbon credits, buyer demand for high-integrity local credits, and the prioritisation of carbon, biodiversity, water, or community-based credits. The session aims to raise awareness of current exclusions, generate actionable insights for more inclusive carbon markets, and contribute concrete recommendations to the EIT Food PATH2CC project.

Main contributors: ELEKS, University of Helsinki, Queen's University Belfast, Juntos Farm, PATH2CC Consortium.

Donatello Room

E. BUILDING ROBUST AND FLEXIBLE MRV

• E7. Soil Carbon Modelling for Scalable and Reliable MRV: Insights from MRV4SOC and MARVIC Projects

Keywords: MRV, modelling, uncertainty, scalability, RothC, croplands, CRCF alignment.

This session shares results from the MRV4SOC and MARVIC projects supporting the development of CRCF methodologies. It involves soil-centred and ecosystem models, with and without Earth observation data assimilation. Topics include model performance, parametrisation, validation against long-term experimental data, uncertainty analysis, and scalability across croplands and agroforestry systems. Case studies illustrate challenges related to error propagation, scale effects, and harmonisation. The session provides scientific insights into how modelling approaches can support transparent, cost-effective, and robust MRV systems for European carbon farming.

Main contributors: CREA, Research Centre for Agriculture and Environment (Firenze, Italy), Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, ILVO, CSIC, GMV.

Galileo Room

- **E8. SCF-TRUSTAI 2026: Artificial Intelligence for Trustworthy Soil Carbon Monitoring and Informed Investment Decisions**

Keywords: Holistic evaluation, farm proficiency, fair rewards, beyond carbon.

The transition to carbon farming and regenerative agriculture is increasingly limited by data confidence and the ability to turn environmental outcomes into robust investment decisions. This interactive workshop explores how artificial intelligence (AI) can enhance monitoring, reporting, and verification (MRV) for soil organic carbon (SOC), enabling credible carbon accounting and high-impact program design with strong returns on investment. The session will demonstrate how to build an AI-based SOC monitoring pipeline, combining remote sensing, in situ measurements, multi-source data fusion, and machine learning for SOC prediction, with careful attention to uncertainty, validation, and auditability. Participants will also see how AI and modelling can translate MRV outputs into actionable decisions for companies and project developers: guiding investments, prioritizing practices, quantifying ROI, and de-risking finance across agricultural supply chains. The workshop concludes with a co-created “Data-to-Decision Checklist” to help participants assess AI-enabled MRV readiness and investment decision-making in carbon farming.

Main contributors: Multitel - Research & Technology Innovation Center (Belgium), Regrow Ag.

Antenore Room

- **E9. Innovations in Earth Observation (EO) for Carbon Farming MRV systems**

Keywords: MRV systems , Carbon farming, Earth Observation (EO), Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF), Co-benefits and trade-offs, Agricultural hedgerows, Satellite imagery (Pléiades Neo), GHG inventories (LULUCF), Methodology harmonization

This panel explores how Earth Observation (EO) and in-situ data can support credible, scalable MRV systems for carbon farming and carbon removals under the CRCF. Speakers discuss recent developments in EO-based monitoring, the demand for spatially consistent indicators of carbon stock change, and the role of EO in assessing co-benefits and trade-offs. The session examines MRV approaches across the three CRCF ecosystem categories—peatlands, agricultural soils and agroforestry, and tree planting—and highlights how methods are adapted to ecosystem-specific challenges. Case studies include EO-based hedgerow detection and efforts to improve national GHG inventories through harmonised research infrastructures. The session concludes with reflections on research cooperation and methodology harmonisation as enablers of credible carbon markets.

Main contributors: European Space Agency, Airbus Space Digital – Geospatial business, Climate Analytics Finland Ltd,

Mantegna 1 Room

[YouTube](#)

INNOVATION SESSIONS

• F2. Innovation Session: On-the-Ground Impact, Regenerative Practices, Biodiversity, and Ecosystem Co-Benefits

Keywords: Nature Credits, MRV, Carbon Farming, Agroecological Transition, Biodiversity Co-Benefits, Transaction Costs, Payments for Ecosystem Services.

Description:

- Unlocking Biodiversity and Nature Crediting Opportunities in Carbon Farming (Meo Carbon Solutions GmbH).
- Agro Carbon: Enhancing Sustainable Agriculture through Carbon Farming (Agro Carbon).
- Carbon Footprint Measurement, Carbon Credits and Reforestation Projects as Integrated Solutions for Climate Action (CO2 REVOLUTION).
- Why Soil Health, its Real Time Monitoring and the True Cost of Carbon Sequestration, Storage Must Be Central to the EU Voluntary Carbon Cert (BIONUA).
- Transforming Agriculture for a Healthier, Sustainable and Tastier World (Doktar Technologies).
- Scaling Measured Soil Carbon Sequestration Projects in Bulgaria: Lessons from Carbonsafe's Experience (Carbonsafe JSC).
- Today's Agriculture in Africa (A. R Brenya Company Ltd).
- From Practice to Scale: Lessons and Insights from aeeco's Peatland Restoration Portfolio (aeeco GmbH).
- Turning Soil Health into Climate Impact: Delivering High-Integrity Carbon Credits Through Regenerative Agronomy (Gaiago SAS).
- Scaling Carbon Farming Program and Resilient Agriculture While Ensuring Scientific Robustness Through Technologies (MyEasyFarm).
- Nature Based Solution Removal Project Development and Marketing (Anew Climate).
- Field Insights on Uncertainty Management in Carbon Farming Projects to Guide the Design of the European CRCF (Agrosolutions).
- MRV Certification Framework Workshop (Klim GmbH).
- Scaling Sampling Design for Carbon Farming MRV (Agricarbon).
- From Trust to Transformation: Data-Driven Carbon Project Ratings and Impact Indices for a Credible EU Carbon Market (CarbonAI Limited).

Main contributors: Meo Carbon Solutions GmbH, Agro Carbon, CO2 REVOLUTION, BIONUA, Ecobase, Doktor Technologies, Stantec (on behalf of CINEA), Carbonsafe JSC, A. R Brenya Company Ltd, aeeco GmbH, Gaiago SAS, MyEasyFarm, Anew Climate, Agrosolutions, Agricarbon.

Carraresi Room

[YouTube](#)

Parallel Sessions 5 – Thursday 19th 9.00 – 10.30

A. FROM PRACTICE TO IMPACT

- **A9. Opportunities for Cooperation on Agroforestry Carbon Farming Between European Research Projects, and Extension to Projects Operating in Africa**

Keywords: agroforestry, MRV, roots, allometry, radar biomass estimation, high resolution imagery, CAP incentives, low value wood residues.

This session facilitates knowledge exchange among European agroforestry research projects addressing MRV challenges for carbon farming certification. Through a series of lightning presentations followed by a panel discussion, participants share approaches, lessons learned, and common bottlenecks related to CRCF implementation and emerging Nature and Biodiversity Credit frameworks. The session also explores opportunities for collaboration with EU–Africa research projects working on agroforestry, carbon farming, and extension. By identifying shared methodological challenges and future priorities, the session aims to strengthen coordination, avoid duplication, and support scalable, scientifically robust agroforestry carbon farming across regions.

Main contributors: European Agroforestry Federation (EURAF), Thünen Institut, Technical University of Munich (TUM), ecosostenibile.eu S.r.l. Società Benefit, AfroGrow, CSIC.

Giotto Room

[YouTube](#)

B. THINKING BEYOND CARBON

- **B8. Bridging the Gap: Farmer-Led Innovations as True Game-Changers**

Keywords: Farmers; agroecological transition; agroforestry; generational renewal; capacity building; EU projects.

This session highlights farmer-led innovations that are already driving agroecological transitions, often without being labelled as “carbon farming.” Drawing on experiences from EU projects and farmer organisations, the panel focuses on real transformation happening on the ground. The discussion addresses capacity building for new entrants through tailored training and digital learning tools, peer-to-peer knowledge exchange between pioneering and newer farmers, and more inclusive engagement strategies. Particular attention is given to reaching farmers currently disconnected from subsidy systems while better supporting those already participating. By foregrounding farmer experience rather than technical jargon, the session aims to reconnect carbon farming debates with practical, long-standing agroecological practices and farmer realities.

Main contributors: European Agroforestry Federation (EURAF), Smart Carbon Farming / Ver de terre production.

Galileo Room

[YouTube](#)

- **B9. Beyond Carbon Farming: Measuring, Verifying and Financing Nature Co-Benefits through Robust MRV frameworks - for Farm to Wetlands and Landscapes**

Keywords: Regenerative Agriculture, Monitoring Reporting and Verification (MRV), Financing transition, Nature Credits, JRC Farming practice evidence library, Wetland restoration, Peatland, Multibenefit accounting, Biodiversity.

This session focuses on how carbon farming and regenerative practices deliver additional benefits for soil health, biodiversity, water systems, and ecosystem resilience. It examines how practice- and outcome-based frameworks, combined with MRV systems, can define, measure, and reward these co-benefits at farm and landscape scale. Drawing on applied examples from agriculture and wetlands, including LIFE projects and biodiversity markets, the session explores trade-offs between scientific rigour, scalability, and transaction costs. Contributions from scientific, implementation, and policy perspectives highlight how beyond-carbon accounting can strengthen business cases and inform the development of credible European frameworks for nature-positive finance.

Main contributors: Soil Capital, Joint Research Centre - European Commission, Cà Colonna srl, Aeco GmbH representing LIFE BiodivCrew, Nattergal, Fundación Global Nature.

Carraresi Room

[YouTube](#)

C. STANDARDS, POLICY, AND OWNERSHIP RIGHTS

- **C4. Approaches to Designing Regional Carbon Certification Schemes**

Keywords: Certification schemes, regional level, result-based, farmer-led.

This session examines different regional approaches to designing carbon farming and carbon credit certification schemes. Building on initiatives from Catalonia, the Netherlands, Switzerland, Veneto, and Canada, speakers compare result-based and practice-based remuneration models, farmer-led initiatives, and governance arrangements. The discussion explores how monitoring, certification methodologies, and emerging standards can support locally adapted yet interoperable soil carbon markets. By contrasting experiences across regions, the session highlights lessons on trust-building, subsidiarity, and alignment between farmers, regulators, and private-sector actors.

Main contributors: EIT Food (on behalf of Veneto Agricoltura), ChrysaLabs, Institute of Agrifood Research and Technology (IRTA), Research institute of organic agriculture FiBL, ZLTO (Smart Carbon Farming Interreg).

Petrarca Room

[YouTube](#)

D. FINANCING CARBON FARMING AT SCALE

• D8. Scaling Carbon Farming with Stakeholders: Trust, Certification Frameworks, and Local Initiatives

Keywords: Trustworthy carbon farming schemes, willingness to pay, certification, low carbon assurance, risk mitigation, co-benefits and sustainability indicators, verification rules, carbon farming pilots, Local carbon credits, MRV, B Corp network, Public-private partnerships.

This panel addresses key barriers to scaling carbon farming, including MRV complexity, certification credibility, governance challenges, and limited farmer trust. Drawing on evidence from Horizon projects, private certification schemes, and local initiatives, speakers present stakeholder perspectives on MRV requirements, willingness to pay, and policy coherence. Case studies include holistic certification frameworks integrating soil health, biodiversity and water quality, local carbon credit schemes, sector-specific certification approaches, and public-private action platforms. Together, these examples illustrate different pathways for operationalising MRV principles, governance arrangements, and financing mechanisms. The session aims to bridge gaps between scientific design, policy frameworks, and market implementation.

Main contributors: University of Teramo Flemish Action Platform For Carbon Removal & Carbon Farming, 4C Services GmbH, Aequilibria srl - SB, ISCC, University of Louvain, Soil Capital.

Mantegna 1 Room

[YouTube](#)

• D9. Financing Carbon Farming: Insights from a Global, Regional, and Local Perspective

Keywords: Carbon farming financing, Carbon farming stakeholders, Financial design, The Generational Contribution, Global-Regional-Local perspectives, Biodiversity co-benefits, Contracts, Knowledge-gaps, Incentives, Scaling, Public and private finance, Carbon farmers, Policy makers, Operators.

This session presents five complementary perspectives on financing carbon farming, spanning global mechanisms, European research, regional studies, and national examples. Speakers examine how carbon farming contracts can be designed to increase farmer participation, address knowledge gaps, and improve incentive structures. Topics include the role of corporate finance in bridging public funding gaps, the integration of biodiversity co-benefits, and the economic viability of carbon farming for small and medium-sized farms. By connecting policy makers, farmers, operators, and companies paying for carbon outcomes, the session provides insights into financial design choices that influence participation, scalability, and impact across different governance levels.

Main contributors: University of Bologna, University of Ferrara, Ruralis - Institute for Rural and Regional Research, BETA tech centre, University of Vic – Central University of Catalonia, Initiative 1415.

Mantegna 2 Room

[YouTube](#)

E. BUILDING ROBUST AND FLEXIBLE MRV

• E10. Standards, Practices, and Certification Approaches for Carbon Forestry

Keywords: Improved Forest Management (IFM); Carbon Farming; EU CRCF; LULUCF; Forest Carbon Certification; Dynamic Baselines; MRV; Additionality; Permanence; Leakage; Forest Resilience; National Carbon Registries; Voluntary Carbon Markets; Nature Credits.

This merged session explores how Improved Forest Management (IFM) can deliver credible carbon removals under the CRCF and LULUCF Regulation. It connects on-the-ground forest management practices with methodological challenges such as baseline setting, additionality, permanence, leakage, and cost-effective MRV. Through participatory discussion, scientific analysis, and case studies, the session examines how EU-level certification, national registries, and voluntary standards can be aligned. Emphasis is placed on governance coherence, climate resilience, and integrity across Europe's diverse forest contexts, providing insights into how forest carbon certification can be scaled while maintaining trust and transparency.

Main contributors: Benefit, Climate KIC, CREA, I4CE, Etifor | Valuing Nature, University of Lorraine, Verra, University of Strasbourg, AgroParisTech, CNRS, INRAE, BETA Climate, Economics Chair, University of Cambridge, Gold Standard, FSC International, European Commission (DG CLIMA).

Palladio Room

• E11. Data Standardisation and Harmonisation towards Credible MRV systems

Keywords: Standardisation, harmonisation, FAIR, vocabularies, metadata, soil, farm management data, keywords, ontologies, transfer functions, tools and formats, sampling.

This session explores data standardisation and harmonisation for Tier 3 model-based MRV (Monitoring, Reporting, and Verification) systems, which require large, diverse datasets for calibration, running, and validation. Efficient use and sharing of soil, land use, management, and climate data—collected via field, lab, or remote sensing—depend on systematic collection, standard formats, vocabularies, and appropriate aggregation or disaggregation. Standardisation underpins FAIR principles, enabling reusability, interoperability, and harmonisation, which reduce errors when combining datasets from different sources. The session presents recent advancements and best practices, with introductory presentations by experts covering MRV data assessment, benchmark sites, sampling design, and the operationalisation of standardised vocabularies. Participants will engage in breakout groups to discuss challenges and co-develop solutions, followed by a plenary wrap-up. The session aims to foster interaction among stakeholders and advance the alignment of standards and tools, supporting more reliable, efficient, and interoperable MRV systems for carbon and soil monitoring.

Main contributors: CREA, ILVO, LIST, WENR, DataCove, Aarhus University, eAgronom, SWRI, Soil Capital.

Antenore Room

Poster Session 1 - Tuesday 17th

Thinking beyond carbon

Exploring holistic approaches that put the focus on the co-benefits (environmental and social) of carbon farming.

P1	Food and Health	<i>A. R Brenya Company Ltd</i>
P2	Scaling Circular Carbon Removal for Regenerative Agriculture	<i>Nellie Technologies</i>
P3	Co-benefit of Regen Practices in Türkiye	<i>Life Climate</i>
P4	Under what conditions can carbon farming schemes deliver socio-economic benefits?	<i>UCLouvain, Project : MRV4SOC</i>
P5	Stakeholder Perspectives on Carbon Farming in Mediterranean Vineyards	<i>CREA</i>
P6	Beyond carbon credits: how to motivate younger generations of farmers to implement regenerative agriculture through new forms of training and capacity building.	<i>Ver de terre production</i>
P7	Benefits and risks of carbon farming in Finland	<i>University of Helsinki</i>
P8	Circular Bio-Waste for Water and Soil Remediation	<i>AgriMercarb</i>
P9	Beyond Carbon: Insights from the Lighthouse Farms Network for a Sustainable and Inclusive Agriculture with soil at its core	<i>Re Soil Foundation</i>
P10	Identification and validation of biodiversity indicators for carbon credits qualification in Europe: Insights from the SMURF Project	<i>Preferred by Nature</i>
P11	Compost microbiota enhances rhizosphere diversity and drought resilience in tomato plants	<i>University of Padova</i>
P12	Empowering Dairy Farmers for Regenerative Change: Co-Benefits and Community Transitions Beyond Carbon	<i>Queen's University Belfast</i>
P13	Exploring the Potential of Carbon Farming and Regenerative Transition in Hungary: A Pilot Assessment	<i>Institute of Agricultural Economics</i>
P14	Testing soil health indicators for the certification of carbon farming co-benefits	<i>Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change</i>
P15	Beyond Carbon Sequestration: Integrating Environmental, Economic, and Social Externalities into Carbon Credit Frameworks in the Mediterranean	<i>CENER 21</i>
P16	Leveraging LAI time-series to characterize cover crop phenology in northern Italian agriculture	<i>CNR-IREA</i>
P17	Organic Climate Farming in Italy for climate change adaptation and mitigation	<i>FIRAB, Fondazione Italiana per la Ricerca in Agricoltura Biologica e Biodinamica</i>

Financing carbon farming at scale

Unlocking funding and business models to scale carbon farming.

P18	Matchmaking Farmers & Investors – Building Trust-Based Carbon Value Chains for Scalable, Verified, and Insured CO ₂ Removals	<i>Credible consortium partners</i>
P19	Carbon Farming for Cooperatives and Smallholders - Between Innovations and Possibilities	<i>CinSOIL</i>
P20	Two case studies on agroforestry-based carbon farming by smallholders: Feasibility of sustainable agricultural practices and the need for suitable financing solutions	<i>Sustainable AG Unternehmensberatung</i>
P21	Financing the transition: a data-driven framework for carbon farming investment.	<i>Green Finance (NL) & MEE0 (IT)</i>
P22	Building a methodology for assessing the cost of the carbon transition	<i>Institut de l'élevage</i>
P23	Building a technical, legal and financial architecture for Carbon Offsetting in slow growing forests	<i>Institut de l'élevage</i>
P24	LIFE SUPER EU – Tackling bottlenecks to upscaling peatland restoration in Europe	<i>NABU, Naturschutzbund Deutschland</i>
P25	Forestry voluntary carbon credit market in Italy	<i>CREA-PB</i>
P26	Mapping the evolution of carbon farming projects across Europe: insights from the 2025 European carbon markets barometer	<i>Deloitte</i>
P27	Scaling credible business models for scope 3 decarbonization: the role of Market-based Instruments	<i>SustainCERT</i>
P28	Carbon farming 4.0: innovative business models for a more sustainable and productive agriculture	<i>Politecnico di Milano</i>
P29	Cross-Border Carbon Farming in the Adriatic: Operationalising Payments for Ecosystem Services	<i>Alcina</i>

Building robust and flexible MRV

Developing monitoring tools that are rigorous yet practical.

P30	Field and Remote Sensing Measurements to Reduce Uncertainty in Forest Carbon MRV	<i>University of Helsinki</i>
P31	Cost-Effectiveness Analysis of Methane Mitigation Measures in China's Rice Production	<i>International Food Policy Research Institute</i>
P32	How to boost the economics of SOC sequestration projects without compromising on scientific integrity with Model Assisted Estimations	<i>Seqana GmbH</i>
P33	BovidCO2: A harmonized MRV tool for low-carbon beef cattle farming initiatives in Spain, developed within the LIFE Carbon Farming project.	<i>NEIKER-Basque Institute for Agricultural Research and Development</i>
P34	A Data-Driven Framework for Regenerative Agriculture: Integrating Digital Tools, MRV Systems, and Soil Carbon Modeling	<i>xFarm Technologies</i>
P35	How to boost the economics of SOC sequestration projects without compromising on scientific integrity with Model Assisted Estimations	<i>Seqana GmbH</i>
P36	Towards a Knowledge Exchange Hub supporting Carbon MRV	<i>ESA Stakeholder Engagement Facility</i>
P37	Carbon Twins Platform	<i>Natural Resources Institute Finland</i>
P38	Digital Forest Carbon Twins	<i>Natural Resources Institute Finland</i>
P39	Clarifying Uncertainty Management at the Project Level in the European CRCF	<i>Agrosolutions</i>
P40	Smart Carbon Farming Project - Building an AI-Enabled Technological Framework for Soil Organic Carbon Monitoring	<i>Multitel - Research & Technology Innovation Center (Belgium)</i>
P41	Comparing soil carbon in regenerative and conventional farming: evidence from a global meta-analysis	<i>eCampus University</i>
P42	Greek Living Earth: A National Digital Platform for Soil Carbon Monitoring & Climate-Resilient Farming	<i>Interbalkan Environment Center</i>
P43	Towards the improvement of the MRV system in Poland through the integration of geographically explicit data	<i>National Research Institute</i>

Poster Session 2 - Wednesday 18th

From practice to impact

Practical examples and results from implemented carbon farming projects

P44	AgriPower ROOTS: Community-Based Circular Carbon Farming Through Waste-to-Biogas, Biofertilizers, and Climate-Resilient Cold Storage on Idjwi Island	<i>Congo Peace Academy</i>
P45	Erasmus for Young Entrepreneurs for Carbon Farming	<i>Academy of Entrepreneurship</i>
P46	Undersowing legume cover crops in Mediterranean rainfed cereals: a regenerative organic practice maintaining yields and soil CO ₂ emissions, while suppressing weeds	<i>Università Politecnica delle Marche Arca Srl Benefit</i>
P47	Carbon footprint and stock of coffee production in the Brazilian Amazon	<i>Brazilian Agricultural Research Corporation</i>
P48	Supporting farmers in building of adaptation and mitigation plans	<i>CRPA Soc. Cons. p. A</i>
P49	BioChar to capture Carbon fo Farming in Georgia Association for Farmers Rights Defense	<i>AFRD</i>
P50	Modeling vineyard carbon footprint in Tokaj wine region: design and application of a vineyard-specific calculation tool	<i>University of Tokaj</i>
P51	Carbon Farming practices to increase Soil Organic Carbon in the Emilian Apennines	<i>Research Centre of Animal Production (CRPA)</i>
P52	eco2for: Innovative approaches to forest carbon management for climate mitigation and rural development	<i>Forest and Wood Technology Research Centre (CETEMAS)</i>
P53	Grupo operativo C-OLIVAR	<i>ASAJA</i>
P54	INNO4CFIs: Scaling Carbon Farming through Innovation and Nature-Based Solutions	<i>F6S</i>
P55	Biochar in Ethiopian Farming Systems	<i>DBFZ</i>
P56	Effects and limitations of carbon farming practises - results from a 5-year field study in boreal agriculture	<i>Baltic Sea Action Group</i>
P57	Sustainable EVolution, innovative olive growing practices through carbon farming to enhance the value of Tuscan agriculture	<i>Coldiretti Toscana/ Impresa Verde Srl</i>
P58	Quantifying carbon credits and sustainability co-benefits on small-scale farms	<i>University of Helsinki</i>
P59	From Soil Carbon towards System Sustainability: Integrating SOC Modelling and Life Cycle Assessment to evaluate environmental trade-offs in Carbon Farming	<i>Università degli Studi di Genova</i>
P60	Strategies for the Long-Term Sustainability of Carbon Farming Living Labs: ERSAF's Experience in the LILAS4SOILS Project	<i>ERSAF</i>

From practice to impact

Practical examples and results from implemented carbon farming projects

P61	C-Farming Alliance project: Empowering Europe's Agricultural Transition through Carbon Farming Education and Innovation	<i>ECAF</i>
P62	Carbonate rocks/lime and carbon sequestration by Enhanced Rock Weathering (ERW)	<i>IMA-Europe</i>
P63	Italy's wood carbon: Dynamic MFA for carbon farming futures	<i>University of Padua</i>
P64	The Italian experience of National Association for Organic and Regenerative Agriculture - First results and insights from a farmer-led support model for Carbon Farming	<i>Associazione Nazionale Produttori AOR</i>
P65	Producers facing Climate Action: Feasibility of GHG Reductions and Carbon Removals in the Fairtrade Sugar Value Chain. Case study of El Salvador, Belize and Costa Rica	<i>Sustainable AG Unternehmensberatung</i>
P66	LIFE ClimatePositive - Advancing carbon farming in forestry across Italy	<i>Etifor Valuing Nature</i>
P67	Use of plant residues for carbon farming in the fruit: bioeconomy and biochar	<i>Delta Institute of Applied Ecology</i>
P68	Innovative silvicultural and silvopastoral models for the restoration and enhancement of carbon sinks in post-mining landscapes	<i>University of Oviedo</i>
P69	SCALING BY SEEDING IN SPAIN	<i>Land Life Company</i>
P70	ClimateSmartAdvisors: Connecting and mobilizing the EU agricultural advisory community to support the transition to Climate Smart Farming	<i>CONSULAI</i>
P71	Best Management Practices implemented in cereal cropland to mitigate climate change	<i>ECAF, University of Córdoba</i>
P72	TRAILS4SOIL: Transformative Living Labs for Soil Health: Advancing Regenerative and Conservation Agriculture Across Europe	<i>ECAF, University of Córdoba</i>
P73	Farmers as Pioneers of Carbon Farming: Insights from Polish Field Trials and Stakeholder Reflections	<i>Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation State Research Institute</i>
P74	Integrating Demand-Side Dietary Shifts into Carbon Farming: Reducing Vegetable Oil Consumption for Climate, Health, and Land-Use Co-Benefits	<i>University College Dublin</i>
P75	Fast, easy and longterm removals	<i>Ausgleichsagentur Nord GmbH</i>
P76	The SOILL Learning Journey: Building Capacity for Climate-Smart Soil Management through Living Labs and Lighthouses	<i>Climate KIC</i>
P77	Designing for Transformation: A Framework for Resilient and Sustainable Food Systems within Safe and Just Operating Spaces	<i>Climate KIC</i>

Standards, policy, and ownership rights

Untangling ownership rights, from farmers to buyers of certificates, from inseting schemes to national inventories.

P78	IESS project: quantifying the economic, social, and environmental impact of agroecological tools for soil carbon sequestration	<i>ECAF</i>
P79	Temporary carbon units from carbon farming and EU agri-food climate policy: Assessment of risks, opportunities, and alternatives for promoting carbon farming	<i>Ecologic</i>
P80	How are emerging technologies accepted and used in soil carbon market standards and policies?	<i>ChrysaLabs</i>
P81	Carbon sequestration and co-benefits: evaluating agroecological and regenerative practices for soil health, soil biodiversity, and pathogen protection in Vineyards and Kiwifruit (Vi.Ki. Project)	<i>Deafal</i>
P82	Insights/Learnings from an early soil carbon program between 2018 and 2024	<i>Foundation myclimate</i>
P83	From Certification to Action: Applying the Low-Carbon Label to Peatland Restoration Projects in France	<i>Fédération des Conservatoires d'espaces naturels</i>
P84	Scaling Sustainable Carbon Farming in Europe: Aligning Policy, Technology, and Incentives	<i>B-NL Academy & Consultancy</i>
P85	Rebooting demand for temporary removals	<i>Carbon Gap</i>
P86	Development of a plot-scale tool for assessing and allocating soil carbon removal, GHG emission and biodiversity KPI in agricultural systems	<i>Agrosolutions</i>
P87	Assessing Model Transferability for Tree-Crop Soil Organic Carbon: Cross-Regional Validation and Performance Diagnostics on Lemnos Island, Greece	<i>Aristotle University of Thessaloniki</i>

